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THE INDIVIDUALIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF A FUTURE SPECIALIST

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Масич С. Ю. Індивідуалізація професійної підготовки майбутнього фахівця

У статті на основі аналізу наукової літератури розглянуто суть і особливості процесу індивідуалізації професійної підготовки майбутнього фахівця. Аналіз наукової літератури дозволяє розглянути індивідуалізацію навчання майбутнього фахівця як процес трансформації особистості під впливом внутрішніх та зовнішніх, об'єктивних та суб'єктивних чинників у їх взаємозв'язку, що сприяє розвитку навичок вирішення важливої проблеми професійного розвитку на основі професійного та культурного досвіду. Зазначається, що індивідуалізація має зовнішній та внутрішній аспекти. Зовнішній аспект індивідуалізації включає адаптацію змісту та форм навчального процесу до індивідуальних особливостей студента, надання педагогічної підтримки з метою розвитку його індивідуальності, а також мотивацію студента, що стимулює до зміни себе та змін своєї діяльності. Внутрішній аспект визначає спрямованість майбутнього фахівця на розгортання та реалізацію індивідуальних устремлінь і становлення індивідуальної позиції у власній професійній діяльності. Індивідуалізація здійснюється в процесі педагогічної взаємодії викладачі зі студентом, що враховує як індивідуально-освітній потенціал останнього, так і систему соціальних цінностей, вимог, а також цілей професійної підготовки.

Ключові слова: індивідуалізація, індивід, предмет, професійна підготовка, майбутній фахівець, чинники, простір.

Masych S. Yu. The individualization of professional training of a future specialist.

In the article on the basis of the analysis of scientific literature the essence and features of the process of individualization of professional training of the future specialist are considered. Analysis of scientific literature allows to consider the individualization of the training of a future specialist as a process of transformation of the individual under the influence of internal and external, objective and subjective factors in their interconnection, which promotes the development of skills for solving an important problem of professional development based on professional and cultural experience. It is noted that individualization has external and internal aspects. The external aspect of individualization involves the adaptation of the

content and forms of the educational process to the individual characteristics of the student, the provision of teaching support in order to develop his personality, as well as the motivation of the student, which stimulates to change himself and change his activities. The internal aspect determines the focus of the future specialist on the deployment and implementation of individual aspirations and the formation of an individual position in their own professional activities. Individualization is carried out in the process of pedagogical interaction between teachers and the student, which takes into account both the individual and educational potential of the latter, and the system of social values, requirements, as well as the objectives of vocational training.

Key words: *individualization, individual, subject, professional training, future specialist, factors, space.*

Introduction. Paradigm shift in the system of modern pedagogy orientations identified a number of fundamentally new theoretical problems. One of the most important problems of modern pedagogical formation is development and self-development of the teacher's person, capable to be oriented freely in difficult socio-cultural issue, actively and professionally participate in the educational process. This strategy is embodied in the direction of the content and form of the educational process of the higher pedagogical school in the formation of " "person prepared to the life", which is not only armed with a system of knowledge, skills, and able to think creatively and act self-development intellectually, morally, physically. This requires a shift from someone who is trained in the subject position.

Study of methodological and theoretical problems of modern higher pedagogical education, as well as problems of organization of educational process in higher educational institutions shows that the turn of the student in the subject of his education, to bring his professional training in line with international standards and the new social realities can only be based on an individualized approach to education.

The task. The purpose of this article is to consider the issue of individualization of training of the future specialist.

The results. The analysis of scientific literature has shown that scientific studies in recent years largely directed to the inner world of a student who is committed to disclose their potential, given by nature. The model V. Serikova [1] the student is the subject of life, so the author proposes to provide personal growth of every child to education on the basis of his experience and guide the pedagogical process on the development of self-development and the actual personal characteristics of students. According to the pedagogy of individuality [2] goals, pedagogical patterns, means of training and education must meet not only the needs

of society, but also a man with his characteristic inner psychological world. For example, T. Grebenuk [3] substantiate the concept of the formation of individual students – future teachers, which includes a number of important provisions: psychologising about the training of future teachers; on the formation of a coherent individuality of the future teacher on the basis of specific situations, allowing him to take a stand; the change of position of the student – the future teacher in the course of vocational training.

On the basis of personality-oriented provisions have been developed pedagogical interaction theory (L. Bayborodova, V. Belkina, V. Dyachenko, N. Radionova, etc.). The principles of the organization which are aimed at optimizing the process of student subjectivity, student, searching for opportunities and ways realization of individual potential of each of them.

Analysis of the psychological literature suggests that the concept of "individualization" is interpreted ambiguously. So, in modern encyclopaedic editions in treatment individualizations proceed from Latin word *individuum* that means "individual", "separate person", "person" [4; 5]. Depending on which of these concepts is accepted as a generic, individualization of the content can be understood as the selection of the individual or individuals on its individual properties; isolation of the individual, the formulation of its individual, uniqueness and originality; taking into account the characteristics of each individual; formation of personality. For this reason, formed a variety of approaches to the definition of individualization, and, using the same term, different authors put different meanings to it.

M. Kholodnaya and V. Shadrikov [6; 7] consider individualization within the subject approach as the subjectivation, that is, formation of the person as a subject. According to M. Kholodnaya [6, p. 13], individualization of learning, based on the subject approach, aimed at creating the conditions for the opening and the formation of the individuality of each child. From the point of view V. Shadrikova fundamentally new way of individualization of training at the macro level is to develop the principles and ways of qualitative transformation of the content of education according to the type of thinking and level of development of student abilities [7, p. 72-83]. V. Slobodchikov and E. Isaev prove that individualization – a "self-determination and isolation of the individual, its separation from the community, the formulation of its individual, uniqueness and diversity" [8, p. 353].

Analysis of works devoted to the philosophical foundations of individualization, indicates the presence of a number of specific meanings, as follows: a) philosophical principle; b) the general method of knowledge; c) form of existence; g) process, inherent in the historical development of mankind. Scientists believe that as a philosophical principle of individualization affects the fundamental questions of life, cognition, activities, that is, has an ontological, epistemological and practical sense. As a general method of learning individualisation leads to the comprehension of the whole through the analysis of its individual elements. Personalisation as a form of life, not only determines the existence of the objective world, but also explains how the development in nature and society, carried out the formation and development of the human personality.

Currently, the prevailing understanding of the philosophical science of individualization as a process immanent historical development of mankind, revealing the strength and ability of a person and going through overcoming the limited social and role of its membership of the development of human values [9].

T. Burlakova [10] in his study conducts a detailed study of individualization. The author found that individualization is described by a variety of concepts, content and nature of which are multi-valued, and in definitions and understanding them is no unity. These include: differentiation and integration, which form two sides of individualization, but have their limits: when infinite differentiation of the individual and society leads to individualism, excessive integration of their personality dissolves in weight leads to conformism; centralization, which is that the level of development of the human personality is directly dependent on the individual's ability to dominate them, to subordinate its power single goal. The role of centralizing the core structure of an individual performs his inner "I", which supports its individual integrity and self-identity in a variety of environmental conditions. In the development of a person changes and biologically, and socially, but thanks to the "I" perceives itself at the same time united and integrated, capable of ensuring the integrity of the individual consciousness in different situations, in a collision of opposing ideas and aspirations; typing – is the assimilation by the individual himself to other individuals; specification – the desire for self-expression and originality; autonomy: the problem of individualization then appears as if a single individual raises the question, has the whole within their own mode of existence, the capacity for self-determination and

self-regulation. Man builds his identity for myself, but at the same time for others. It is not individualized to completely inward, and to assert themselves in society [10].

E. Vesna in her research highlighted a number of definitions of individualization contained in psychological studies [11, p. 56-58]. Here are some of them: individualization – is individuation, comprehension and overcoming unconscious conscious, the development of the self; individualization – this integration, the establishment of a balance, a balance between individual needs (instincts, innate aspirations and priorities) and social demands, between the social and the biological in the personality structure; individualization – this sublimation, that is, the deployment of individual aspirations, trends in the social environment, to overcome its opposition, search and formation of exit mechanisms that aspirations; individualization – is the existence of, or individual being of the individual, is an ongoing, intimate process; individualization – is the realization of the unique nature of the person, its creative expression; individualization – is the development of unique life strategies, meanings and styles of activity, reflecting the nature and level of adaptability of the person; individualization – this is the highest level of socialization of personality, reflecting its ability to social creativity, to the introduction; individualization – is intimidations, social inclusion in the deep layers of the personality.

E. Vesna presented the following stages of individualization [11, p. 117]: a deliberate refusal to follow the norm – isolation; comprehension – an appeal to the individual indefinite knowledge (intuition); valuation of the sample with a view to its transfer, the inclusion of social value – externalization. The author believes that the difficulty faced by the person requires a search for ways out of the problem situation. The successful resolution of the difficulties you need to appeal to internal reserves, credibility, self-reliance and a willingness to creative.

Analysis of the scientific literature suggests that training individualization process should be focused not only on the formation of formal logic and cognitive activity-structures, but also on the formation of values and meanings and subjective-personal structures. Thus it is necessary to refer to the approval of B. Bratus, that "fractures and changes in development occur at a time when there is a mismatch between the cash capabilities, knowledge and skills and the system of semantic connections with the world" [12, p. 10]. Thus, the driving force behind development is the contradiction between the need-motivational sphere and operational-technical

side of leading activity. There is also a need to address the subjectivity of the individual measures, which implies the ability to be self-initiated activity and life. It should be noted that the development of human subjectivity is both a natural and artificial process [8]. This subjectivity can be considered for the process of the scheme (as a natural time sequence of stages, periods, stages) and the structure of the activities (as a set of methods and means of development, which are determined by goal setting).

We know that the opportunity to become a subject of educational and professional activities realized in the process of internalization of external controllers (norms, rules, values) in the internal controls of the student activity. The effectiveness of this process depends on the adequacy of its individuality of the future teacher, which is determined by the coincidence of the character, strength, volume of external influences the characteristics of the student's personality, as well as providing its positive development.

Recognition of student subject necessitates awareness of each person's uniqueness, the integrity of his personality, willingness to accept it as such, who is endowed with a kind of potential for development and a variety of qualities, as well as recognition of the right of everyone to the subjective perception of their own development, individual choice of ways and purposeful control of their own learning activities.

Conclusion. Thus, the individualization of training the future specialist should be seen as a process of transformation of the individual under the influence of internal and external, objective and subjective factors in their relationship that promotes the development of skills to solve the important problem of professional development on the basis of professional and cultural experience. The individualization of vocational training of future specialist this implies on “inside” level is supplied by means of positive changes of his individuality, inside personal growth, self-development and self-improvement. On this reason they wrote V. Slobodchikov and E. Isayev. The authors, exploring the issue of individualization of spiritual life of man, say that "radical and profound transformation of any fragment of his self; any mental ability is tested for authenticity and inalienable part of their true, inner self of man" [8, p. 168].

The analysis of scientific literature allows us to characterize the nature and specifics of external and internal sides of individualization, as well as to determine their opportunities for professional development and the development of future specialist. The most valuable in this regard is the study of T. Burlakova, in which the author

defines the individualization of training of future teachers as a process that promotes vocational education student and a positive change in his inner world in order to provide a basis for self-realization in educational activities and life in general. The author points out that individualization as any pedagogical process, characterized by the interconnection and interdependence of the outer and inner sides thereof. The outer side of individualization involves adapting the content and form of the educational process to the individual needs of students, provision of pedagogical support in order to develop his personality and motivation, which is able to induce the student to change themselves and change in their activities. The inner side is the focus of the future teacher in the deployment and implementation of individual aspirations and the formation of individual positions in their professional activities [10].

Customization is carried out in the course of pedagogical interaction of the teacher and the student. It is necessary to take into account the individual student's educational potential, as well as the system of social values, requirements and training purposes.

The main feature of the outer side of individualization is to create a situation of choice, as well as in a direction facing the student. Its orientation, as well as the nature and characteristics of motivation contributed to the fact that the external educational space taken by the student. Understanding, rethinking imagery and symbolism of outer space, the development of the information received is happening in the inner space of the individual. The integrity of the perception of the inner space expands personality fills its content and meaning. In turn, the richness, fullness and integrity of the interior space are sources of internal movement and the development of individuality and personality. Opening up new perspectives, meanings, creative transformation. Starts movement "from the student," which consists in the implementation of its unique nature, creative self-expression, as well as the development of new life and professional meanings.

Individualized educational environment and, accordingly, organized learning process are external controls inside of the individualization of the student. Customization of training future teachers is provided to "domestic" level via an internal student of personal growth and self-organization of its personal (educational and developmental) space. Vector "internal component personalization" is directed by the student and provides him with a productive interaction with the world and

himself. The inner side of individualization is associated with the disclosure of the student's personality, the specifics of its spiritual world [10].

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